

IMPROVED METHODS FOR SHIPBOARD EVALUATION OF ANTIFOULING PAINTS

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ABSTRACT

Improved methods have been developed for the shipboard evaluation of antifouling paints capable of extended service exceeding five years. Underwater photographic documentation enables the close-up study of antifouling paints while the ship remains in-service. Test panels secured to the outboard side of the bilge keel permit the testing of a large number of candidate antifouling paints under actual service conditions. Underwater measurements of roughness have provided revealing histograms that permit the comparative evaluation of ablative antifouling paints. The suspected environmental impact of the organotin antifouling paints has imparted new impetus to the development of ablative paints targeted to calcareous fouling organisms.

1. INTRODUCTION

Under the Navy Shipboard Energy Program progress has been made in the service evaluation of antifouling (AF) paints¹. Improved methods employed in the evaluation of AF paints reflect the development of new perspectives in the formulation of these paints. Several events that highlight changes in the development of AF paints may be noted as follows:

Green Layer

The premature failure of the Navy's standard copper/vinyl AF paint (F-121) was found to be due to a thin layer of insoluble green copper compounds that formed on the surface of the AF paint rendering it nontoxic and susceptible to fouling². Work underway at DTNSRDC is directed towards formulating a cuprous oxide AF paint that would not form an obstructing copper precipitate on its surface.

Controlled Release Coatings

The older AF paints were essentially a physical mixture of the toxicant and polymer matrix. A more elegant development of AF formulation was the molecular attachment of the toxicant to the polymer for controlled release.

Ablative Mechanism

A notable advance in AF paint formulation was a dual approach to toxicant release by the use of the ablative mechanism in conjunction with appropriate controlled release toxic compounds.

A Broad Spectrum Toxic

Considerable effort in the past has been directed towards the search for a toxic lethal to a broad spectrum of fouling organisms³. In recent years there has been an increasing concern that such toxicants may be harmful to non-target organisms in the aquatic biosphere.

2. TEST SHIPS

The use of ships to evaluate the performance of AF coatings prior to this decade was limited to inspection of ship hulls in drydock after a period of service⁴. The shipboard evaluation as presently conceived includes periodic waterborne inspections of the hull for the full service period culminating in the final drydock inspection.

Stripe Test

Candidate AF paints are applied as stripes to selected Navy surface ships as shown by a typical paint layout plan in Figure 1. Each AF paint includes a stenciled area as shown in Figures 2 and 3. Within this area surface changes are documented by underwater close-up photography and roughness measurements taken in drydock and underwater.

Bilge Keel Panels

Test panels secured to threaded studs butt welded to the outboard side of the bilge keel are used to evaluate antifouling performance under ship operating conditions. Each panel assembly, coated on both sides with antifouling paint is 10 by 12 by 1/8 inches with four corner holes to secure the panel to four studs with conventional lock nuts and washers. A 1/4-inch thick wafer of zinc with a central steel cored

hole is fitted as a spacer to each stud in metal to metal contact with the underside of the test panel to provide cathodic protection of the mounting hardware and insure proper electrical grounding of the panels to the hull, which is also under cathodic protection. Figure 4 shows an array of panels on the bilge keel of a test ship.

Figure 1. Ship Layout of Antifouling Test Coatings

3. ANTIFOULING TEST PAINTS

A number of candidate AF paints applied as test stripes to ship hulls or as test panels on bilge keels are being evaluated. These AF paints can generally be characterized by the manner of toxic release and how the toxic is incorporated within the paint film.

Leaching

The first successful antifouling paints formulated by the Navy and still in use rely on the leaching mechanism for release of the toxic cuprous oxide⁵. The cuprous oxide was physically dispersed within the paint film. The rate of toxic release was excessively high at the beginning, gradually diminishing until the occurrence of calcareous fouling within a period of 20 to 30 months indicated failure.

Figure 2. Typical Detail of Stenciled Location

Hydrolysis

New Navy organometallic polymer (OMP) antifouling paints have been formulated where the organotin toxic compound has been chemically reacted to suitable polymer chains⁶. The toxic bound to the polymer matrix migrates from within the film to the surface, where it hydrolyzes to provide long term protection with minimal change in paint film thickness and expenditure of the toxic.

Ablative

The toxic of an ablative paint is chemically attached to the polymer backbone of the paint matrix. Sustained antifouling capability is achieved by the combination surface erosion by water flow to expose fresh toxic and its subsequent hydrolyzation. Ablative paints have potentially two desirable characteristics: one is that the surface roughness is controlled by hydrodynamic erosion and the sloughing action may assist in removal of toxic resistant surface macrofouling attachments.

4. PHOTOGRAPHIC DOCUMENTATION

Close-up color slides or photographs can quickly record the condition of the various stenciled areas of the paint stripes on a ship hull or the test panel secured to the bilge keel. A composite of the slides can reasonably represent the entire stenciled area and the fouling as it occurs from the boottop to the keel. A slide can also show the condition of each panel or a close-up of a selected area on the panel. Examples of various types of photographic documentation are as follows:

Figure 3. Test Ship In Drydock Showing Stenciled Locations

Composites

Figures 5-7, listed below, each present a composite of the stenciled area of an AF paint stripe after eight months of service.

Figure 5 - Navy OMP AF paint

Figure 6 - Commercial Tributyltin Ablative AF Paint

Figure 7 - Commercial Copper/Cuprous Oxide Ablative AF Paint (with slimicide additives).

Normal Bilge Keel Panel Photos

Figure 8 presents two commercial ablative AF paints each represented by a set of three panels. The AF paint of one set contains a copper compound with antislime additives while the AF paint in the second set contains tri-tin compounds as the toxic component.

Close-Up Bilge Keel Panel Photos

Figure 9 provides a close-up view of a representative section of three bilge keel test panels. Each panel is coated with one of three AF paints; a standard Navy copper/vinyl paint, a Navy OMP paint and a commercial organotin/ copper ablative AF paint.

5. ROUGHNESS

The manually operated British Maritime Technology (BMT) hull roughness analyzer (HRA) was used to measure the roughness of antifouling paints while in-service. This instrument provides a string of maximum peak to valley height readings reflecting hull roughness, parameters that are crucial to hydrodynamic drag^{7,8}. Each value represents the vertical distance from the highest peak to the lowest valley over each increment of two inch travel of the stylus over the surface. The measuring head is comprised of a stylus supported by a trolley as shown in Figure 10. It is manually rolled in a forward and aft direction over the stenciled area at each three foot vertical level as illustrated in Figures 2 and 3. At least 30 peak to valley data points are provided per horizontal pass.

Figure 4. Bilge Keel Panel Array

Histogram Analysis

The large number of data points are graphically

analyzed as a histogram to show a scale of increasing magnitude and frequency. Five parameters were defined from the histogram to represent the roughness data that can be tabulated for a given stenciled area of an AF paint. The first parameter is the mode (value occurring most frequently) for all the roughness data compiled for a given stenciled area. The second parameter is the median (the middle value) for all the data up to a cut-off of 500 microns. Using this same cutoff the third and fourth parameters are the percent frequency of data points calculated for the mode and median. The fifth parameter is the percent hull roughness attributable to the hull primarily independent of the paint and considers all the data above 500 microns. The author recognizes that at the cut-off of 500 microns, the roughness changes in the AF paint overlap with the defects that develop in time with the AF paint. The histograms in Figures 11 and 12 show baseline roughness and roughness after eight months of service respectively.

Figure 5. Composite of Navy Organometallic Antifouling Paint

Figure 6. Composite of Commercial Tributyltin Ablative Antifouling Paint

6. RESULTS

The selection of photographic documentation and roughness histograms are part of an extensive compilation of information on record at the Center. Their presentation in this paper is intended to show general trends in AF paint evaluation and development.

The two longest performing AF paints that have prevented calcareous fouling on Navy surface ships are the Navy OMP AF paint and a commercial tributyltin/cuprous oxide ablative AF paint. Figures 5, 6 and 7 show that after 8 months of service the non-ablative OMP paint is beginning to foul with slime and algae from the boottop to the twelve foot level while the two commercial copper ablative AF paint with slimicide and the tri-tin/cuprous ablative AF paint appear to be free of any visible fouling.

Figure 8 shows comparable paints after 27 months of service on bilge keel test panels. The ablative paint appears to be equally effective in both the copper (slimicide) and tri-tin/cuprous oxide formulations.

Figure 9 typically shows the improved performance of the commercial ablative tri-tin/cuprous oxide AF paint over the non ablative Navy OMP and copper/vinyl (F-121) AF paint on bilge keel test panels after 42 months of service.

Figures 11 and 12 show two histograms of a commercial copper ablative (slimicide) AF paint which is also represented as a composite in Figure 7. Figure 11 depicts the baseline roughness which shows the typical positive skewness of a newly applied AF paint. Figure 12 shows an increase in positive skewness indicating that the AF paint is becoming less rough and is ablating. This increase in positive skewness can also be shown by the quantitative changes in the first four parameters. Generally a decrease in roughness will be indicated by a decrease in the mode and median accompanied by no change or by an increase in their respective percent frequency. Although small differences in AF paint roughness can be measured it is not yet known what affect each increment of hull roughness may have on ship drag at different ship speeds. The common presumption in AF paint development and evaluation is that the coatings that become smoother in-service and still prevent visible fouling for the longest term will demonstrate the preferred ablative characteristics.

Figure 7. Composite of Commercial Copper/Cuprous Oxide Ablative Antifouling Paint

Copper (Slimicide)

Tri Tin Cuprous Oxide

Figure 8. Bilge Keel Panels After 27 Months of Service

Copper (F-121)

Navy OMP

Tri Tin Cuprous Oxide

Figure 9. Close-Up of Bilge Keel Test Panels After 42 Months Service

Figure 10. Traverse of Measuring Head Over Hull Surface

Figure 11. Histogram of Baseline Underwater Roughness of Copper Ablative Antifouling Paint

Figure 12. Histogram of In-Service Underwater Roughness of Copper Ablative Antifouling Paint After 8 Months

7. OTHER CONSIDERATIONS

Shipboard evaluations enable the selection of the AF paints on the basis of long term performance. However, there are three other characteristics that will also play a roll in the ultimate selection as follows:

Verifiable Quality Control

The new technology AF paints are more complex in chemical structure. Chemical analysis techniques for paints are being developed and adopted by the Center. With the application of these analytical techniques, the critical internal components of AF formulation can be identified to establish criteria for assuring reproducibility of manufacture and the maintenance of proper quality control in procurement.

Life Cycle costs

The increase in the cost of AF paints as reflected by their degree of toxicity is governed by: the extent of protective gear and precautions taken by personnel in its preparation and application; the disruption of scheduling of other work during drydock hull maintenance and repair; and finally the procedures used to remove and dispose of the hull coating.

Environmental Impact

The environmental impact issue is unresolved at this time. The demonstrated effectiveness of the ablative mechanism does increase the likelihood that toxicicants can be found that are more benign to the environment but targeted specifically to calcareous fouling⁹.

8. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

o Shipboard evaluations of AF paints enable the reliable determination of AF paint fouling resistance and film performance.

o The use of bilge keel test panels provides a realistic approach for the evaluation and development of ablative AF paints for long term service.

o The roughness of an ablative paint can be monitored and measured while the ship remains in-service.

o Although OMP AF paint can achieve long term service capability by sole reliance on its toxic component, ablative AF coatings can potentially improve service life and surface roughness characteristics.

o Use of the ablative mechanism in combination with less toxic biocides shows promise for the development of eminently acceptable long term AF paints and should be explored vigorously.

9. REFERENCES

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